

Thiodiazines.

Part I.

Condensation of Thiosemicarbazide with ω -Bromacetophenone.

BY

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Thiodiazole derivatives have been studied by numerous investigators chiefly by Max Busch and his collaborators, but there is lack of information regarding the chemistry of thiodiazines. An examination of the literature showed that of the six possible classes of thiodiazines, a few representatives of the following three types only are known, namely,

Schrader (J. pr. Chem., 1917, [2], 96, 180) obtained a derivative of 1:2:3-thiodiazine by condensing *o*-cyano-benzenesulphonyl chloride with hydrazine. Again a derivative of 1:2:4-thiodiazine has been obtained by the oxidation of 2-phenylimino-3-phenyl-tetrahydrothiazole, (Kucera, Monats., 1914, 35, 137; compare also Schrader, J. pr. Chem., 1916, [2], 95, 392); while the only derivative of 1:3:4-thiodiazine is that obtained by Frerichs and Förster (Annalen, 1910, 371, 236, 255). It might be mentioned here that the so-called 1:3:4-thiodiazines obtained by the condensation of potassium aryl-sulphocarbazines with ethylene dibromide (Busch, Ber., 1894, 27, 2509, 2516; Busch and Lingenbrink, J. pr. Chem., 1899, [2], 60,

219, 225) have afterwards been proved to be arylhydrazones of cyclic dithiocarbonic ester (Busch and Lingenbrink, J. pr. Chem., 1902, [2], 65, 473). Another so-called thiodiazine derivative, 2-amino-4-phenyl-5-keto-dihydro-1 : 3 : 4-thiodiazine obtained by condensing phenylhydrazine with sulphocyanacetic acid (Harries and Klamt, Ber., 1900, 33, 1154) has been shown by Freichs and Förster (*loc. cit.*) to be a thiohydantoin derivative. Evidently, excepting the very few derivatives of the thiodiazines referred to above, no other representatives of this class of compounds are known. An investigation has therefore been taken up with a view to obtain further knowledge on the subject. In the present communication, which is of a preliminary character, the condensation of thiosemicarbazide with ω -bromacetophenone has been described and the constitutions of the reaction products determined.

On boiling an alcoholic solution of the reactants in molecular proportion, the hydrobromide of a base of the empirical composition, $C_9H_9N_3S$ (m. p. 125°) separates in brownish-yellow needles melting at 196° , while the mother liquor on being treated with acetone in the cold gave a crystalline hydrobromide (m. p. $225-26^\circ$ not sharp,) of another compound of the empirical formula $C_{11}H_{13}N_3S$ which melted at 123° .

The condensation of ω -bromacetophenone with thiosemicarbazide might lead to the formation of the following possible isomeric compounds.

The absence of acid character of the substance, (m. p. 125°), coupled with its inability to lose sulphur when boiled with alkaline lead solution or freshly precipitated yellow mercuric oxide, precludes the possibility of its possessing a -NH-CS-NH or -NH-CS-N= residue in the molecule as represented in formulæ (II) and (III) (compare Guha, J. Am. Chem. Soc., 1922, 44, 1511). Moreover, it is well-known that a halogenated ketone acts on thiocarbamides forming compounds containing sulphur atom in the ring (compare Walther and Roch, J. pr. Chem., 1913, [2], 87, 27). Again the compound under discussion has been found lacking in the capacity to condense with acetone or anisaldehyde, which should not be the case, had it possessed any free hydrazino group as formulated in (IV) and (V). On the other hand, the chemical evidence based on its actions towards phenylthiocarbimide, carbon disulphide and benzene sulphonyl chloride points definitely to the presence of a free amino group in the molecule. All these facts are best interpreted by the formula (I), which has consequently been assigned to the compound.

2-Amino-5-phenyl-1:3:4-thiodiazine (I) is a strong monoacid base and forms well-defined salts with acids. It gave a picrate and an aurichloride. The acetyl and benzoyl derivatives are soluble in alkali.

Attempt was made to prepare the isomeric acetyl compound, 2-amino-5-phenyl-3-acetyl-1:3:4-thiodiazine, by the action of ω -bromacetophenone upon 1-acetylthiosemicarbazide. The reaction took place readily in alcoholic solution producing the hydrobromide of an acetyl compound which is soluble in alkali. The alkaline solution, however, unlike that of its isomer, develops a beautiful greenish-blue colour on exposure to air, which turns pink on being acidified. On boiling with an excess of dilute hydrochloric acid, the acetyl compound

hydrazone (VI), and the base, $C_6H_5N_3S$, m. p. 167-68°, to be 2-keto-4-phenyl 2:3-dihydro-1:3-thiazole hydrazone (IV). The condensation of thiosemicarbazide with ω -bromacetophenone becomes therefore interesting in as much as it leads to the simultaneous formation of a five-membered as well as a six-membered heterocyclic ring.

With respect to the mechanism of condensation, the author suggests that the first stage consists in the addition of the bromoketone to the sulphur atom of the thiosemicarbazide with the formation of an intermediate sulphonium derivative. (Compare, Dixon and Taylor, T., 1912, 101, 2502; Walther and Roch, J. pr. Chem., 1913, [2], 87, 27). This is followed by the elimination of hydrobromic acid forming S-phenacylthiosemicarbazide, which in the final stage loses a molecule of water resulting in ring closure, which might occur in two ways, thus:

The proportion of the thiodiazine and the thiazole derivatives, the author is inclined to think, will depend on the relative basic character of the two amino groups present in the thiosemicarbazide molecule. Since the basic character of the 1-amino group is much more enhanced than that of the 4-amino group, the main product of reaction is the thiodiazine, the quantities of the thiodiazine and the thiazole derivatives being actually in the ratio, 5 : 1. It follows from what has been assumed that the condensation of thiosemicarbazide derivatives in which the basic character of the 1-amino group has been suppressed will result in the formation of a thiazole

derivative. The production of the acetyl derivative of 2-keto-4-phenyl-2:3-dihydro-1:3-thiazole hydrazone from 1-acetyl-thiosemicarbazide and ω -bromacetophenone confirms this deduction.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Thiosemicarbazide and ω -Bromacetophenone: Formation of 2-Keto-4-phenyl-2:3-dihydro-1:3-thiazole-isopropylene hydrazone (VI) and 2-Amino-5-phenyl-1:3:4-thiodiazine (I).—4.5 grams (1 mol.) of thiosemicarbazide and 10 grams (1 mol.) of ω -bromacetophenone were heated under reflux with 50 c. c. of dry ethyl alcohol for 15-20 minutes. The dark reddish-brown solution was then concentrated to nearly one-third its volume and cooled, when clusters of brownish yellow needles of the hydrobromide of (I) began to appear. These were freed from the mother liquor, washed with dry ethyl alcohol and finally with acetone. The yield of the crude hydrobromide, m. p. 192-95°, was about 8.6 grams or about 64% of the theoretical. The mother liquor was diluted with its own volume of dry acetone and the colorless plates (m. p. 225-26°) of the hydrobromide of (VI) which immediately began to appear, were collected after an hour. The yield was about 2.1 grams or about 14% of the theoretical. The latter hydrobromide was dissolved in hot water containing a few drops of methyl alcohol, filtered and the solution made alkaline with sodium carbonate. The crystalline precipitate of 2-keto-4-phenyl-2:3-dihydro-1:3-thiazole-isopropylene hydrazone (VI) was crystallised from dilute methyl alcohol in colorless hexagonal plates melting at 123°, which turned reddish brown on exposure to light for some time. (Found: C=62.20; H=5.85. $C_{12}H_{13}N_3S$ requires C=62.35; H=5.63 per cent.).

The former hydrobromide (m. p. 192-96°) separates from a 95% alcoholic solution by the addition of ether, in snow-white needles melting at 197°, after the usual treatment with animal charcoal. (Found: N=15.27; Br=29.86; S=11.34. $C_6H_{10}N_3SBr$ requires N=15.54; Br=29.41; S=11.77 per cent.). To obtain the free thiodiazine the crude hydrobromide (8.6 grams) was dissolved in about 150 c.c. of warm water and allowed to stand for an hour. The solution was then filtered to remove a small amount of a brownish yellow impurity and made alkaline with a solution of sodium carbonate. The solution at once turned milky and within a few minutes gave a mass of colorless needles of *2-amino-5-phenyl-1:3:4-thiodiazine* (I). These were filtered after half an hour, washed with cold water and dried on a porous plate. The compound was purified by repeatedly dissolving in cold dilute hydrochloric acid filtering off any insoluble matter and precipitating with dilute sodium carbonate solution. It melted at 125-26°. (Found: C=56.80; H=4.69; N=22.05; S=17.07. $C_6H_9N_3S$ requires C=56.55; H=4.71; N=21.99; S=16.76 per cent.). The base is very soluble in most organic media from which it is difficult to obtain it in the crystalline form on dilution with suitable solvents. On exposure to air, (especially when moist) or in solution, it gradually turns brown owing to oxidation.

The *hydrochloride* of the base separates from a mixture of alcohol and ether in colorless rectangular plates melting at 205° decomp. (Found: Cl=15.44; S=14.18. $C_6H_{10}N_3SCl$ requires Cl=15.60; S=14.07 per cent.). The *picrate* was obtained in the form of golden yellow plates melting at 215° decomp., on mixing the components in alcoholic or acetone solution. The *aurichloride* was obtained by treating a hydrochloric acid solution of the base with a dilute aqueous solution of auric

chloride. It crystallised from hot water in golden yellow needles melting at 166-67° decomp. (Found : Au = 37·19; Cl = 26·30. $C_9H_{10}N_3SCL_4Au$ requires Au = 36·98; Cl = 26·79 per cent.).

The *acetyl* derivative was obtained by treating the base with acetyl chloride in pyridine solution in the cold. From glacial acetic acid it separates in colorless needles melting at 172-73°. (Found : N = 18·07. $C_{11}H_{11}ON_3S$ requires N = 18·03 per cent.). The *benzoyl* derivative, obtained in a similar manner, crystallises from dilute pyridine in colorless needles melting at 170°. (Found : N = 14·7; $C_{16}H_{16}ON_3S$ requires N = 14·24 per cent.). The acetyl and benzoyl compounds are soluble in aqueous alkali; acids precipitate them from solution in white amorphous mass.

2-Amino-5-phenyl-1:3:4-thiodiazine and Methyl Iodide.—A methyl alcoholic solution of the base was heated with an excess of methyl iodide under reflux for 5-6 hours on the water bath when the hydroiodide of 2-methylamino-5-phenyl-1:3:4-thiodiazine (?) separates in colorless needles. It was recrystallised from 95% alcohol and ether in colorless prismatic needles melting at 223° decomp. (Found : N = 13·09; I = 39·11. $C_{10}H_{12}N_3SI$ requires N = 12·62; I = 38·14 per cent.). The hydroiodide of the ethylation product, which crystallises in colorless rectangular plates and melts at 234° decomp., could be similarly obtained. These hydroiodides are soluble in hot water. On treating the aqueous solution with alkali or sodium carbonate colorless oils were obtained which failed to crystallise.

2-Amino-5-phenyl-1:3:4-thiodiazine and Phenylthio-carbimide : Formation of

The reactants were heated in alcoholic solution in molecular proportion for a few minutes, when yellow crystals of the above thiocarbamide separated out. From pyridine it was obtained in bright yellow plates melting at 179-80°. (Found: N=16.65. $C_{10}H_{14}N_4S_2$ requires N=17.18 per cent.).

2-Phenylsulphonylamino-5-phenyl-1:3:4-thiodiazine.—

To one molecule of the above base were added two molecules of alcoholic caustic potash and then with constant shaking an alcoholic solution of one molecule benzene sulphonyl chloride. The reaction was completed by heating on the water bath for a few minutes. On cooling colorless needles were obtained. These were recrystallised from alcohol, the first fraction being rejected. The product which appeared to be the potassium salt of the complex sulphonamide was however not very pure. (Found: S=9.82. $C_{15}H_{19}O_2N_3SK$ requires S=8.68 per cent.). It was very soluble in water. The free sulphonamide could not be obtained pure owing to its hygroscopic nature and extreme solubility in water and other organic media.

2-Amino-5-phenyl-1:3:4-thiodiazine and Carbon Disulphide: Formation of

A mixture of the base (1 mol.), alcoholic caustic potash (1 mol.) and carbon disulphide in excess was heated on the water bath under reflux for 8-10 hours. The excess of carbon disulphide was distilled off, the liquid separated from a small amount of an oily residue and the free dithiocarbamic acid precipitated by acidifying with dilute hydrochloric acid. The yellow product was dissolved in aqueous alkali, treated with animal charcoal and reprecipitated by hydrochloric acid. From absolute

alcohol it separates in yellow needles melting at 181-82° decomp. (Found : N=15·97 ; S=35·30. $C_{10}H_9N_3S_3$ requires N = 15·73 ; S = 35·96 per cent.).

The *monomethyl* derivative was obtained by dissolving the dithiocarbamic acid in the calculated amount of methyl alcoholic potash and heating under reflux for half an hour with an excess of methyl iodide. The reaction mixture on being concentrated by evaporation deposited the methyl ether in bright yellow hexagonal plates, which melted at 159°, after crystallisation from dilute pyridine. (Found : C=46·76 ; H=4·09. $C_{11}H_{11}N_3S_3$ requires C=46·98 ; H=3·92 per cent.)

1-Acetylthiosemicarbazide and ω-Bromacetophenone : Formation of 2-Keto-4-phenyl-2:3-dihydro-1:3-thiazole-acetylhydrazone.—Equimolecular quantities of the components were heated in *dry* alcoholic solution for a few minutes. On cooling the *hydrobromide* of 2-keto-4-phenyl-2:3-dihydro-1:3-thiazole-acetyl hydrazone was deposited in colorless needles melting at 234-35° decomp. The hydrobromide was dissolved in 80 per cent. alcohol and treated with an excess of aqueous ammonia when the free acetyl compound was obtained. It separated from hot alcohol, after treatment with animal charcoal, in pinkish needles melting at 196-97° decomp. (Found : C=56·08 ; H=5·16. $C_{11}H_{11}ON_3S$ requires C=56·65 ; H=4·72 per cent.). The acetyl compound is soluble in alkali. The alkaline solution develops a beautiful greenish blue colour in presence of air, which turns pink when acidified. The colour totally vanishes after a few hours.

Hydrolysis of 2-Keto-4-phenyl-2:3-dihydro-1:3-thiazole-acetylhydrazone.—The acetyl compound was heated with a large excess of dilute hydrochloric acid (2N approx.) for about an hour until a test portion on being made alkaline with caustic soda and shaken with air did not turn blue. The whole solution was then made alkaline

with caustic soda when *2-keto-4-phenyl-2:3-dihydro-1:3-thiazole hydrazone* (IV) was precipitated in dirty white needles. This was rapidly filtered at the pump, redissolved in dilute hydrochloric acid, filtered from a small amount of brown oxidation product and precipitated with sodium carbonate solution. It was finally crystallised from alcohol in long colorless needles melting at 167-68°. (Found: C = 56.00; H = 4.24. $C_9H_9N_3S$ requires C = 56.55; H = 4.71 per cent.). It possesses strong basic properties and forms well-defined salts with acids. The moist base on exposure to air turns brown owing to oxidation.

2-Keto-4-phenyl-2:3-dihydro-1:3-thiazole hydrazone and Acetone: Formation of (VI).—The reactants were boiled together for a few minutes and the solution evaporated to dryness. The brown residue was taken up with methyl alcohol, decolorised with animal charcoal, and precipitated by cautious addition of water in hexagonal plates melting at 123°. The substance turns brown on exposure to light. (Found: N = 17.87. $C_{12}H_{13}N_3S$ requires N = 18.18 per cent.).

2-Keto-4-phenyl-dihydro-1:3-thiazole-anisal hydrazone.—This was obtained by the condensation of *2-keto-4-phenyl-2:3-dihydro-1:3-thiazole hydrazone* and anisaldehyde as a beautiful yellow compound when a dilute hydrochloric acid solution of the hydrazone was shaken with anisaldehyde. From alcohol it separates in pinkish white needles melting at 225° decomp. (Found: N = 13.35. $C_{17}H_{18}N_3S$ requires N = 13.59 per cent.).

Condensation of Acetoneethiosemicarbazone and ω -Bromacetophenone: Formation of (VI).—1.3 grams of the former and 2 grams of the latter were boiled under reflux with 30 c.c. of *dry* alcohol for about 15 minutes. The condensation product separated from the boiling mixture in colorless plates melting at 235° decomp., and appeared to be identical with the hydrobromide (m. p. 225-26° not

sharp) obtained by the addition of acetone to the mother liquor of the condensation product of thiosemicarbazide and ω -bromacetophenone. The hydrobromide was dissolved in very dilute (10%) methyl alcohol and poured into a dilute solution of sodium carbonate. The crystalline precipitate was thoroughly washed with water and finally crystallised from dilute methyl alcohol in hexagonal plates melting at 123° . (Found: C=62.80; H=5.86. $C_{12}H_{13}N_3S$ requires C=62.35; H=5.63 per cent.).

Hydrolysis of 2-Keto-4-phenyl-2:3-dihydro-1:3-thiazole-isopropylene hydrazone: Formation of (IV).—The hydrazone was boiled for a few minutes with concentrated hydrochloric acid and the solution was evaporated to dryness on the water bath. The residue was taken up with cold water, filtered and made alkaline with sodium carbonate. The resulting base was several times recrystallised from alcohol until the melting point reached 168° . (Found: N=22.03. $C_9H_9N_3S$ requires N=21.99 per cent.). This compound was found to be identical with the product of hydrolysis of 2-keto-4-phenyl-2:3-dihydro-1:3-thiazole-acetyl hydrazone (*vide supra*).

The work is being continued with substituted thiosemicarbazides and monochloracetone, monochloracetal and esters of α -halogenated acids

In conclusion, I take this opportunity of expressing my sincere thanks to Sir P. C. Rây for his keen interest throughout this investigation.

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[Received May 29, 24].
